

PERFORMING ARTS IN UZBEK FOLK INSTRUMENTS DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

Uzbek national instruments and their promotion of the performing arts around the world are becoming more widespread. In this article you will learn about the past and present of the performing arts in Uzbek folk instruments.

Ethnic, cultural and musical Uzbek musical culture of each nation has a centuries-old history and has been formed over the centuries, as well as the history of its creation and its formation, present and future. It is known from history that all the peoples of the world have their own culture and art, as well as musical culture, which is their spiritual wealth. In particular, the musical culture of the peoples of the East formed the basis of the national music of each nation, had a school of theoretical and practical performance. Certain series of musical performances, such as maqom, mugam, navba, raga, kyui, which are the musical riches of the peoples of the East, have been performed and developed in different periods in different forms and directions.

Independent country has the opportunity to preserve folk and highly classical professional music, to develop in the spirit of the new age and to promote it not only in our country, but also on the world stage.

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan, as in all spheres of social life, has undergone radical changes in the field of culture, which has created great opportunities for the development of culture, both in form and content. Respect for the spiritual values of our people, their preservation and development, the desire for our sacred religion, traditions, historical, scientific and cultural heritage have risen to the level of state policy. The State Conservatory of Uzbekistan (2002), the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater (2002) adopted a number of resolutions and decrees on the development of pop music, and the sacred names of many thinkers and scholars were restored. The fact that the anniversaries are widely celebrated at the international level is a practical manifestation of the state's care for the development of culture.

Uzbek national instruments and performing arts around the world is becoming more and more widespread. In particular, the People's Artist of Uzbekistan, holder of the Order "For

Great Services" Turgun Alimatov and his son Alisher Alimatov performed Uzbek classical melodies on tanbur, dutar and sato in 1991 in the United States . In 1996 he performed in Germany, in 1995-1997 in England and in 1997 in France.

Founded in 1991, the "Sog'diyona" State Chamber Orchestra of Folk Instruments "The Great Silk Road" is a new tradition of interrelationships between ancient Eastern and Western musical cultures . He started his activity with the lofty goal of continuing the period. Over the years, the orchestra under the direction of artistic director and conductor F.Abdurahimova has given concerts in Germany, Spain, Egypt, Turkey and performed not only Uzbek melodies on national instruments, but also samples of world classical music. .

In accordance with the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov dated October 20, 1995 "On measures to support and encourage the further development of theater and music in Uzbekistan" In order to develop the art of dance, the Uzbeknavo Tour Concert Association (renamed the Uzbeknavo Variety Association in 2001) was established in 1996. Training of qualified specialists for all spheres of art, cultural and educational institutions has always been in the center of attention of the first President of the Republic .

Thanks to independence, radical changes have taken place in all spheres of science, and our national traditions and national values have been restored. People have a new way of thinking, a new look and a new way of thinking. In particular, significant changes have taken place in our national musical art. In particular, the holding of the symphonic music festivals "Ilhom - XX" and the international music festival "Sharq taronalari" on the territory of Uzbekistan is of global significance.

It should be noted that the number and value of the orchestras of folk instruments of the new period, which have a place in the performance practice of music in Uzbekistan , is growing day by day. Prior to independence, there were two major professional groups in the country - the State Academic Orchestra of Folk Instruments named after Tukhtasin Jalilov (1938) and the State Orchestra of Folk Instruments named after Doni Zokirov (1957). Now the number of such teams is growing significantly every year . In particular, in 1991 the chamber orchestra of Uzbek folk instruments "Sogdiana", in 2000 the orchestra of folk instruments under the "Uzbek dance", in 2011 "Navruz", in 2015 and the chamber orchestras of folk instruments "Istiqlol Yoshlari" began their creative activity. In these orchestras, which have a repertoire in accordance with the composition and capabilities of the team, the performance practice is enriched on the basis of new approaches.

After independence, unprecedented changes are taking place in the cultural life of the Republic. In particular, the revival of forgotten national values, centuries-old ceremonies and traditions, the 2750th anniversary of ancient and eternally young cities - Samarkand, 2500th anniversary of Bukhara, Khiva, Karshi and Tashkent, the 2000th anniversary of Margilan, as well as the 1000th anniversary of the Alpomish epic the holding of large conferences devoted to it is a clear proof of this idea. Currently, a number of exhibitions such as "Uzbekistan - my homeland", "Echo of the centuries", "Masters of our art", "You are the only one, the holy homeland", "Rainbow stars", "Tones of the motherland", "Nihol" Along with the important role in the spiritual life of our people, the holding of elections is also important in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation that loves its homeland and is loyal to its people.

Young talented musicians and singers have won international competitions and festivals around the world is a testament to the great attention paid to art in our country. At the same time, it is gratifying that the centuries-old artistic traditions of Uzbek music and its ancient commonality with the music of the peoples of the East are increasingly reflected on the international stage. The Sharq Taronalari International Music Festival, which has been held in the ancient city of Samarkand every two years since 1997, has played an important role in this. As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov said, "Oriental music is an Eastern philosophy, an integral part of the Eastern world. The role of Oriental music in the world cultural heritage is enormous ... For thousands of years, this music has been purifying people's hearts and raising their spirits."

Since 1996, due to the expansion of the number of participants, this date has been held throughout the country. Finally, since 2001, it has become a festival of multi-voiced ensembles and orchestras. Since 2008, the festival has been called "Echoes of Navruz." The event was organized by the International NGO "Healthy Generation", the Creative Association "Tasviriy Oyna" (2008), the Swiss Cooperation Office of the Swiss Embassy in Uzbekistan (2012), the United Nations Information Center (2015) and Kamolot. "Youth social movement (2017) began to help.

Since 2015, the festival has become an international event. The festival was attended by creative teams of preschools, children's music and art schools, music colleges and academic lyceums, as well as universities. Our colleagues from Karakalpakstan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan also visited with their art groups. For six days, each artistic team demonstrated their performance skills. Introductory classes on national instruments were also held. Given the increase in the number of teams and participants, listening to them has been split in two, starting in 2016, with music colleges, academic lyceums and university art groups in a couple of years, and preschools in the odd-numbered years. ensembles and orchestras of children's music and art schools will take part in the festival

Summarizing the above considerations, it is appropriate to emphasize the following. The life of the musical art of Uzbekistan in the new era is connected with the radical political, economic and social reforms implemented and being implemented in the Republic. An objective assessment of it shows that the musical environment, on the one hand, is connected with the great flow of socio-cultural processes on the path of national revival and spiritual purification, and on the other hand, faces the difficulties of the transition to a market economy.

An example of this is the personal participation of President Sh. Mirziyoyev in the International Festival "Maqom", which was held on September 6-10, 2018 in Sharisabz. The festival was attended by more than 300 artists from 75 countries. In addition, it was established in 2019 in Bozatov district of Karakalpakstan. From 2021, at the initiative of the President, it has become a tradition to hold the Youth Voice contest "Boztov FEST" to promote the district to the whole of Uzbekistan. In 2021, this competition, which has discovered bright talented young people, is held in the areas of baxshi, traditional performance, opera and variety.

Video conference on the development of school education on January 28, 2021, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that a graduate must know how to play at least one profession and one national instrument. Then he signed a resolution "On additional measures for further

development of culture and arts." According to the decree, starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, students in general secondary education will be taught to play at least one of the national musical instruments, and this will be noted in their certificates. 10,130 schools, 323 children's music schools, 826 cultural centers will be provided with 3 sets of 7 types of national instruments. 205 billion soums will be allocated for this purpose.

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